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Silence After the Waves

It was dark, yet the dazzling lights of the beach resort made the place more exciting. The moon shone brightly, and the stars glimmered above, making the sea look even more captivating. People roamed barefoot on the ivory-colored sand. I could hear the loud laughter of vacationers, the cheers of tinkling liquor glasses, and music moving in rhythm with the dancers. The sea breeze was calm and refreshing, while the waves rolled endlessly.

As the night grew late, the noise slowly faded. Programs ended, and some guests returned to their rooms.

“Let’s get back to our room now,” Daddy said.

We went straight to our room since it was almost midnight. The room was small but enough for four.

“Time to sleep now, little angels,” Mom said, kissing our foreheads.

I was no longer a child. I was already eighteen, and my brother was sixteen. Daddy also bade us goodnight and kissed our foreheads. I closed my eyes and covered myself with a blanket. I tried hard to sleep but failed. I glanced at my parents and my brother. They were already fast asleep. I checked my phone. It was already past three in the morning. I thought of stepping outside to feel the air and calm myself. Quietness might help me sleep. I wore my slippers, brought my phone, and quietly went out.

The resort was silent now. Only the waves could be heard. Though the sky was still dark, the resort lights stretched toward the sea. Wanting to unwind, I walked slowly toward the shoreline. The breeze felt soothing and cool. I forgot to bring a sweater, so I hugged myself as I strolled along the shore. I put my headset on, and listened to mellow music.

No one else was outside. As I continued walking, I accidentally stumbled over an empty liquor bottle.

“Ouch! What was that?” I muttered as I stood up and wiped my shorts.

I remembered the earlier drinking and laughter, but strangely, the area looked clean. No trash in sight. I checked my phone again. It was already 3:50 a.m.

“It’s time to sleep now, Samantha,” I told myself as I removed my headset.

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I turned back toward our room when I suddenly heard a banging sound. I looked around and noticed a small tent near the shore. Curious, I slowly walked toward it. The sound grew louder and more consistent. Though it was dark, I saw a man outside the tent, wearing black, squatting on the sand, clutching a bag as if it were precious. He repeatedly banged steel scissors against an empty liquor bottle.

Something felt wrong. I stared at him, uneasy. Fear crept in, and I decided to return to our room. As I turned around, I stepped on something again and fell.

“Ouch!”

Another liquor bottle lay beneath my foot. I picked myself up and reached for my phone, which had fallen to the sand.

“What are you doing here?” the man asked in a husky voice.

I turned around. He stared at me intensely. I was terrified. I couldn’t speak. My heartbeat raced, and the breeze felt colder. I froze as he stood up and suddenly ran toward me.

I opened my eyes. The moon was shining brightly, and the stars were slowly fading. The sky looked peaceful and beautiful. I felt something rough beneath my skin. As I pushed myself up, I realized I had been sleeping on the sand.

Confused, I searched for my phone, but it was gone. I started walking along the shore. Some vacationers had already woken up. My parents must be looking for me. I headed toward our room when I heard sudden shout.

“A dead body here!”

I stopped. The sun was beginning to rise. People rushed toward the small tent. My curiosity pulled me there too.

“It’s a girl!” a blonde woman exclaimed.

People kept murmuring and asking what happened. I squeezed through the crowd and saw her. She lay on the sand, almost naked. Blood stained her stomach, and wounds covered her arms and legs. Her hair was unevenly cut, leaving her nearly bald. Her face was pale and her shirt and shorts looked familiar.

“She’s too young,” someone whispered.

A man called the police, and minutes later, police officers arrived and blocked the area. Crime investigators followed shortly after.

“Gab, where are you going?” a woman shouted.

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I turned and saw my younger brother running toward the crowd. Mom followed him anxiously.

“There’s a dead body, Mom,” Gab said.

“What? A dead body? Where’s your sister?” Mom asked.

“She was already gone when I woke up,” Gab replied.

I stepped forward. “Mom! I’m here. I just couldn’t sleep.”

She didn’t hear me. They went straight to the crowd. I followed closely.

“Excuse me,” Mom said as she pushed forward.

“Gab... is that your sister’s shirt?” Mom asked, her voice trembling.

“Oh my God... Gab... it’s Samantha!” she screamed.

I froze. The girl was me. Stabbed. Wounded. Nearly naked. My blonde hair cut. I felt nothing. I watched as Mom clung to my body, crying, while police tried to pull her away. Gab ran to call Daddy. When he arrived, he shook with grief. Beside my body lay my phone, headset, bottle, tent, and steel scissors.

Then I remembered.

“I said, what are you doing here?” the man demanded, holding the scissors.

“I... I just wanted to unwind. I couldn’t sleep,” I answered, trembling.

“Have you seen me before?” he asked.

“No,” I whispered.

He dropped his bag. A bundle of blonde hair fell out. Mad, he ran toward me. I felt the scissors stab my stomach. Blood flowed. The stars and moon faded, and everything turned black.

“Daddy? Mommy? Gab?” I called softly.

I watched my family crumble in grief. I tried to hug them but my arms passed through them. I was scared. Then, a gentle wind blew. Near the tent, a girl in white stood smiling at me.